

TechCentral and Inclusion of SMEs and MNCs

Report by coursework students of UTS 94663
Navigating Entrepreneurial Ecosystems and
Initiating Change, 2021 cohort

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Foreword

This report is part of a series of student generated series about entrepreneurial ecosystems. Each report is a derivative of their coursework, conducted in collaboration with multiple industry partners and interviews with stakeholders in the ecosystem. The subject, 94663 Navigating Entrepreneurial Ecosystems and Initiating Change, is a core subject in the Diploma in Innovation at TD School and a popular elective across other UTS degree programs. The subject was piloted as part of the launch for the Sydney School of Entrepreneurship in 2017¹ and draws directly on Martin's prior experience in visualising entrepreneurial ecosystems.²

The subject runs for three weeks in July, during which students are tasked with defining and exploring an entrepreneurial ecosystem, understanding its history and visualising its current state. Based on that knowledge, they then develop proposals that will bring the ecosystem forward.

The reports reflect the work that was presented publicly to invited guests and stakeholders in the subject, as well as members of the public who joined the presentations via the publicly available event page.

Methodology

The cohort of 50+ students was divided into random teams, each of which could choose their own ecosystem to focus on, with the only caveat being that it relates to TechCentral. Generally, the ecosystems were geographically in the immediate vicinity of TechCentral³, but varied significantly in terms of their sectoral focus.

Each team was instructed to consider the types of stakeholder based on Stam's seminal (2015) review of ecosystem factors. The general method of this study follows our own method of evaluating ecosystems that has evolved over years of experience, in consultation with an Australian wide network of ecosystem researchers. While our process is not yet well documented, it is entirely consistent with the 2018 guide produced by the German Society for International Collaboration,⁴ promoted by the Aspen Network of Development Entrepreneurs (ANDE). Teams adopt a qualitative approach, involving interviewing a broad range of participants to extract insights on their interpersonal connections and interrelations between factors and to identify specific opportunities for change. Each participant is believed to have a clear view of their immediate ecosystem, from which teams stitch together the more holistic view of how the ecosystem works.

The method can be tailored to specific ecosystems, ranging from rural communities through to internationally acclaimed innovation precincts. The breadth of Stam's framework and this method enables pushing back against the myth that innovation and entrepreneurship is primarily the domain of high-tech startups and VCs. While they do play a very important role, they are not the only organisations that matter to create economic growth (Brown & Mason, 2017; Spigel et al., 2020).

Field research for coursework follows the same principles as field research for academic purposes. As a result, the students' work mirrored the process of ecosystem research conducted by Martin Bliemel, for which he has ethics approval (HREC# ETH18-3020).

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¹ Bliemel, M., Schweitzer, J., Roy, G., Keitel, A., Nicolas, L., Miles, M., ... & Griffith, S. (2019, November). Herding cats to co-create cross-university courses in record time. *UIIN University-Industry Interaction Conference 2019*. University Industry Innovation Network.

² Bliemel, M. (2019). University-based entrepreneurial ecosystems and their visualisations. *University-Industry Innovation Magazine*.

³ <https://www.uts.edu.au/news/innovation/welcome-neighbourhood-tech-central>

⁴ <https://www.goethe.de/resources/files/pdf197/5.-guide-for-mapping-the-entrepreneurial-ecosystem.pdf>

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1 Evolution of the Entrepreneurial Ecosystem

The nature of the ecosystem has experienced exponential growth throughout Sydney's immense evolution. Thus, it is crucial to identify and analyse key milestones and relevant interconnections, which ultimately facilitated the trajectory of the space. As a result of understanding the fundamental ingredients within the ecosystem's history, crucial conclusions can be drawn regarding its future and rich opportunities worth leveraging. Therefore, the first part of this leverage proposal will evaluate significant events within the history of the ecosystem in relation to Startups, Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) and Multinational Corporations (MNCs).

1.1 History of Startups

The history and evolution of startups in Sydney can be vague and varying as the industry has always lacked a standardisation in classification metrics. Furthermore, the rapid changes and disruptions in the economy over the past 10-15 years have made it difficult to set concrete foundations. As a result, there is little data about startups and their impact on the Australian economy outside of the tech start-up sector (City of Sydney, 2016). According to Start-up Genome's 2019 report, Sydney's Startup ecosystem historically had a high performance, showing particular strength in global connectedness and FinTech. The largest number of Australian startups are in Sydney CBD and the largest talent pool of individuals with business knowledge, technology expertise and creativity are in the city. Now, with the development of TechCentral, ground-breaking innovation is becoming increasingly sought after and a huge potential in economic contribution is seen in the startup hub. Larger corporations are required to propel entrepreneurship, and in recent years, they have helped generate momentum. Companies like Atlassian have made commitments to the cause, leaving stakeholders in the ecosystem hopeful for the future.

Additionally, Startups have played a major role in contributing to the fast-evolving industries of innovative technology and education within Sydney's creative ecosystem. A multitude of government funded partnerships have evolved including Cicada, a science-based innovation program, GATE, a Global AgTech Ecosystem, and Eighteen04 focusing on clean technology (NSW Govt, 2020) in an effort to provide an incubator and co-working space for Australian startups and scaleups. Through these government partnerships, young entrepreneurs are empowered to shape Sydney's innovative future and educate others via a network of connections, expertise and resources.

1.2 History of SMEs

During the 1940- 60s the Sydney economic climate dramatically changed to place itself in a better position to be seen on a global scale. Suburbanisation of manufacturing in the inner city locations were driven out to western areas due to the fact of higher rent prices, congestion and also limited scope for expansion. Moreover, this allowed SMEs and other businesses to relocate to the city or inner city locations. For SMEs the ecosystem began to develop and other larger businesses were attracted to new signs of consolidation and urban renewal changing the function and culture of suburbs. Major Technology shifts have also accelerated Sydney's growth in the SME sector as people can now work more efficiently, reducing time and space with technology.

Our economy has proved its resiliency over the course of the last decade by surviving both internal and foreign economic shocks, such as the global financial crisis. Between 2007 and 2017, the city of Sydney's SME population increased by approximately 4,000. However, this does not negate the fact that our economy faces difficulties that must be addressed in order to sustain continuing growth and Sydney's global reputation as a liveable city. Thus, an economic development strategy has been developed by the council of the City of Sydney, which will contribute to the realisation of the goal for a vibrant, ecologically sustainable economy and a liveable city that benefits SMEs.

1.3 History of MNCs

There is no denying that Australia has gradually transformed into one of the most fertile commercial ecosystems as a result of a strong and reliable economy and thriving business communities. The growing opportunity evident within the Australian economy and culture has provided many Small and Multinational

Corporations) who have played an imperative role in cultivating successful business ventures through funding, guidance and networks.

Some significant events in the Sydney ecosystem include:

- Establishment of Feeder and Exit routes – It is important as it enables MNCs to have access to talent feeders and exit routes allowing them to expand through acquisitions. Assisted by Multinational R&D centres
- Growing government awareness and assistance – The government is beginning to understand the value of start-up communities by investing in startups using tax incentives. Both domestic and international companies are hence encouraged to provide funding and support for startups.
- The overall cultural shift in Sydney within the past 15 years is largely responsible for the current buzz and inherent future blossom. The development of this scene is displayed through start-up communities, networking events, incubators and entrepreneurial spaces and has played a significant role in creating international investment appeal.
- The flourishing of both national and international venture capital firms has been important for start-up spaces to acquire attention and vital funding to transform ideas into reality.

Figure 1: Mapping for Sydney Tech Central Startup-Hub

Companies Leading the Way. (2019, December 4). Crossroads 2020

Producing high impact companies is a major factor in upholding Entrepreneurial ecosystems. With focus on digital tech businesses, Australia has effectively created high-value, highly successful public companies. These companies include Seek (1997), REA (1995) and Carsales.com (1997), which started as small tech businesses and have now combined to make a total net worth of approximately \$25 billion dollars (Figure 2).

Other MNCs including Atlassian (2003), are now worth \$45 billion, listing the software business as the 10th biggest company in Australia.

1.4 Important Milestones

In a world that is dominated by the evolution of technology, it is important that society continuously works together to grow and unite forming an Entrepreneurial ecosystem. Through creativity, society will be able to push global leaders into generating more innovation and create higher value tech firms around the world. Below are some examples of the milestones Sydney based Businesses have achieved since being launched as start-ups.

Milestones. (2019, December 4). Crossroads 2020.

Atlassian	Plans to move its global headquarters to Central Eveleigh. This will be achieved through signing as an anchor tenant at the Sydney Innovation and Technology Precinct.
Athena	Raising over \$70 million in October 2019, the business has been reported to be the largest round of venture funding hosted by Australian VCs.
Baraja	Focusing on LiDAR and self-driving cars, the business has secured \$45 million dollars in funding since 2019. The CSIRO innovation fund and Sequoia China both played major roles in this network.
Canva	Sydney's digital design unicorn, raises its value to \$4.7 billion since launch.
Data Republic	A governing platform for data-sharing led by Singtel Innov8, raising \$23.5 million for the business.
Elenium Automation	Airport check-in automation technology, led by Acorn Capital, raising \$15 million for the company.
Fluent Commerce	Cloud based order management software, produced for retail industries. Series B funding of over \$33 million and led by the US growth equity firm Arrowroot capital.
Practice Ignition	Sydney fintech that develops software used to streamline sales proposals, run by Tiger Global Management, capitalising \$26 million dollars.
Prospa	Venture backed fintech firm, reaching a marketed capitalisation of over \$700 million within its first day of launch.
Salesforce	Contributing over \$50 million to the global venture capital pool for Australia. The business is backed by Dropbox, Stripe and Evernote, and majority supports the Australia Trailblazer Fund.

2 Entrepreneurial Ecosystem Map

2.1 How to Read the Map

For our ecosystem map we have fostered a grassroots concept as a highly insightful hierarchical structure. Shown in our ecosystem map from the ground-up chronology to clearly present in order of power, size and status, the key stakeholders we identified of Sydney's startups, SME and MNC ecosystem. Within this structure, we have further sub-categorised all stakeholders by colour-coordinating them into key sectors as highlighted in the corresponding legend, these include education, government, technological, cultural, industrial and capital. Starting at the bottom, the foundational or grassroots stakeholders of Sydney's startup scene are outlined, these being large organisations, tech companies, public spaces, indigenous communities, educational institutions and public spaces that have an overarching and broad role at all levels of our entrepreneurial ecosystem. Following the grassroots layer is the intermediary component of the map in which the so-called 'middle-man' stakeholders are identified including higher education institutions, government bodies and initiatives as well as startup companies who orchestrate change, regulations and innovate within the ecosystem. Next is the key individuals who are required to make key decisions and oversee operations of the different organisations, startups, SME's, MNC's, government bodies and institutions within our EE. Finally, the core contributors sit at the top of the map as the niche players such as established tech companies NTT, NEC and Atlassian as well as government departments such as NSW Infrastructure, Treasury and City of Sydney. These core contributors each play a fundamental role within the new TechCentral development helping to shape the future of the surrounding ecosystem through the resources, knowledge, regulations and expertise they provide. Moreover the core contributors such as NTT anchor the ecosystem with funding and support from the NSW government.

2.2 Key Findings & Relationships

Our ecosystem map displays the relationships between each stakeholder and their importance within our ecosystem. Starting from the bottom, our Grassroot stakeholders include large organisations, including tech companies, public spaces, Indigenous communities, and educational institutions. These stakeholders create a base for innovation, allowing communities and organisations to work together and form an entrepreneurial ecosystem. Stakeholders such as UTS start-ups and StartupAus, provide both students and communities with the opportunity to put forth their ideas and develop them into start-up businesses. Whereas our intermediary sector just above the grassroots layer, allows stakeholders the opportunity to have a middleman focus on each component. This sector includes higher education institutions, government bodies and initiatives and start-up companies. The Intermediary layer allows businesses the authority to demonstrate change, regulations, and innovation within the ecosystem.

Most intermediary stakeholders have a strong tech-based background, thus linking them to TechCentral and their connection to the grassroots stakeholders. The key individuals layer, was used to make key decisions and oversee different operations for organisations, startups, SMEs, MNCs, Government bodies and institutions. Whereas, the top layer of Core Contributors allowed niche players to assist in portraying innovation and sustainability within the community. Overall, it is displayed that the main connection and key finding of the map is that the majority of the stakeholders in each category have a strong focus on innovation and sustainability and stem from tech based backgrounds.

3 Leverage Proposal

3.1 (Big) Why & What

Our team's vision over the next ten years for the entrepreneurial ecosystem of Sydney's startup, scaleup, SME and MNC scene surrounding TechCentral entails two key outcomes. First, is to create a more collaborative and supportive environment for sustainable startups to emerge. As stated in an interview we conducted with Operations Manager of UTS Startups, Emma Earley, TechCentral should aim to transition upcoming startups away from a focus on revenue, investment and employment but instead to foster a more sustainable ethos looking at creating a more positive impact on the environment, ecosystem and surrounding communities. Since TechCentral is constantly evolving and forward thinking, our proposal aims to provide sustainable startups, scaleups, SMEs and MNCs with progressing green innovations. This will be achieved by providing access to technologies, connections, co-working spaces and resources for these startups to contribute to the general well being of the community, evolution of society and in meeting the current sustainable development goals.

Second, is to enhance inclusivity of the TechCentral development by extending its current criteria from being exclusive only to STEM students instead opening the innovative precinct to a broader variety of students from a multitude of different disciplines, faculties and backgrounds. By eradicating the gatekeeping restrictions on the precinct, the TechCentral community will be greatly enriched through invaluable contributions from a wide range of students from a diverse range of disciplines such as art, business, law, management as well as DAB (design and architecture). This is a highly significant leverage opportunity for the precinct as this will enable it to achieve its goal as a hub for the next generation to shape the future and create new sustainable startups.

3.2 How & When

3.2.1 Issue 1: Tunnel Vision on Technological Innovation

In the development of TechCentral and the EE in Sydney, there is a huge focus on the potential of tech-startups and their role in nurturing the Sydney Startup Hub to rival that of Silicon Valley and reviving the Australian economy post-COVID-19. After our team's analysis of the ecosystem's evolution, future goals and stakeholders, we have identified a huge and arguably overly-narrowed focus on entrepreneurial innovation from a technological perspective. The current Chief of the Industry Advisory Team for Tech Central has expressed in an article that he does not believe in pursuing technological innovation for technology's sake, however many aspects of the ecosystem have led us

to believe that more could be done to ensure this is avoided. We understand that there is an indisputable potential in software and IT innovation for GDP growth and job creation, especially with FinTech in Sydney's context. However, among the widespread enthusiasm and growing appetite for advancement in technology from both the public and private sectors, there are a lot of voices that don't have the same level of agency in the conversation regarding TechCentral or even in the EE, that also have potential. Our team interviewed some ecologically sustainable startups and asked them what kind of support they had received or was available to them. Despite Australia's comparatively low rate of angel and venture capitalist investment (Recke & Bliemel, 2017), Bodhi Kawulia, co-founder of EYWA stated that there is a plethora of funding resources available from startups; for example, from the NSW government there are grants available from TechVouchers and 'Minimum Viable Product' (MVP) and from the private sector there are accelerators (StartMate, Climate Solutions Accelerator etc.), venture capital (Blackbird, Airtree Artesian etc.) and angels/family offices (Grok Ventures, Sydney Angels Network etc.). However, she also stated that the support is only really available to the 'right' kind of startup, which usually translates to a software product or a technological twist on an existing business model. The support quickly shrinks for ideas outside of this scope (Winn, 2021).

Although we're aware that there is a space for ecological startups in Sydney's Startup Hub, it is not a corner of the EE that is spoken about enough. The Australian economy may have experienced major setbacks, but so did its progress towards the Sustainable Development Goals and Sustainable Sydney 2030. Furthermore, Australia's shift away from fossil fuels and towards more green jobs is an ongoing issue today, and highlights that such concerns shouldn't be overshadowed by other incentives. The City of Sydney has dozens of action plans that have demonstrated the issues they are aware of and want to address. Among these include the Tech Startup Action Plan 2016, as well as environmental sustainability-related plans such as the Environmental Action 2016-2021: Strategy and action plan and cultural enrichment plans such as Creative City cultural policy and action plan 2016. After close analysis of these documents, we noticed that there is little connection or collaboration between these objectives. The fragmentation between the council's strategies does not optimise each plan they should, or the wellbeing of satisfaction of stakeholders holistically.

3.2.2 Lever 1

The co-founder of Urban Plant Growers, Dilhan Wickremanyake, stated in an interview that in the startup space, investors most often invest in incremental improvements on what already exists. He believes that software products are so heavily invested in because they are generally low-risk and don't have high costs attributed to them in comparison to business ideas that are building something brand-new. For ecologically sustainable startups, there aren't really any standardised metrics for sustainability (Winn, 2021), which makes it harder to garner investors and support. Our proposal is for the public sector to introduce a new grant specifically for ecological startups, selecting the recipient to be one with a business model that most positively influences society and has the potential to tackle the global market. This includes business models based on green tech as well. This grant will demonstrate the government's initiative towards environmental sustainability and broaden the narrative surrounding innovation. As the EE grows, the appetite for high-risk also grows (City of Sydney, 2016), therefore government initiative will encourage large corporations and private investors to take interest too. It will also help kickstart increased focus on sustainability in the startup hub, and there will be more regulations and set standards for the measurement of sustainability. This will ultimately lead to value creation for the local community and greater society as these startups are largely values-driven. A study showed that "the majority of the ecological startups (more precisely 77%) create sustainable value as they employ value creation for sustainability. In other words, most entrepreneurs exploit ecological opportunities not only to maximize profit, which would require traditional value creation, but also to create economic, ecological, and social value by integrating these values within their business model for sustainability (Shane and Venkataraman, 2000; Dean and McMullen, 2007; Schaltegger et al., 2012)" (Kuckertz, Berger & Gaudig, 2019). The grant should encourage people from all backgrounds to apply by proposing how their business model will tackle social issues and be profitable. We believe it should rival other grants, so be valued at around \$15-20k and also offer a continuous support system that provides knowledge and resources, to ensure scale-up. The ongoing support will ensure that value creation for the community was achieved.

Rather than just holding Silicon Valley, Sydney has the potential to gain a competitive edge in the global scene through this approach.

3.2.3 Issue 2: Selective Opportunity for STEM Students and Lack of Diversity among Stakeholder Visibility

While studying the future state of the EE and the vision for Tech Central, we noted that there is an aim of encouraging 25000 students to focus on Science Technology Engineering and Maths (STEM) and life sciences (The Premier, 2020). In the EE, among tertiary educational institutions, UTS Startups plays a key role in providing local talent with having the most innovative startups each year. In our interview with Emma Earley, she stated that UTS Startups has members from every faculty at UTS; although Engineering and IT students make up the largest discipline in the space, about 29% of all members are from the Business faculty, 8% are from Arts and Social Sciences, 8% from Transdisciplinary and 5% from Law etc. We believe that educators should take more initiative in supporting a more diverse range of students in their potential future with TechCentral. From a general survey we conducted among our peers, we discovered that none of them were aware of the development of TechCentral despite constantly engaging with EE directly or indirectly on a regular basis. At UTS, there is already an emphasis on sustainable practice in every faculty. However, remote learning and working has proved that human interaction and intuition has never been more essential in the workplace and collaborative environments. The job market is quietly creating thousands of job opportunities for people who can bring the human touch to the rapidly evolving high-tech future (Anders, 2017).

3.2.4 Lever 2

We propose that TechCentral collaborates with educational institutions to spread awareness about its development as well as encourage involvement from students. Similar to opportunities already present at UTS, for example, such as the Lucy Mentoring Program, Build Program, Accomplish Award etc. a program that nurtures local talent for innovation and creative intelligence. The program should be over one academic year and include teams ranging from individuals as well as groups such societies, clubs and collectives; both independent and collaborative learning should be encouraged in a dynamic manner. Students will be encouraged to critically analyse TechCentral and link back to a social issue in the EE they care about and how they can tackle it via innovative and creative thinking. The highest performing teams will be networking and work experience opportunities at Tech Central. We believe that this will prove to be a great platform for the younger generation to be a part of the conversation.

Furthermore, in the EE, different stakeholders and aspects influence each other, therefore we believe the City of Sydney's plans' should be more contrived of each other. Among the voices and figures that lead the conversation surrounding the development of the EE, we also believe that there should be more proactive inclusivity of different stakeholders. For example, ecological startups and other startup types, SMEs in the local area, the residential community as well as the local Indigenous elders. The educational program will allow students to highlight and give agency to these stakeholders and play meaningful roles in the precincts continual evolution and development.

3.3 Who

The potential activators selected to pull levers and utilise their interconnections for this proposal include Atilla Brungs, David Thodey and Monica Barone. All three of these stakeholders play a major role in ensuring the future of both innovation and sustainability in the world and therefore have been chosen to help with creating an entrepreneurial ecosystem for TechCentral.

Atilla Brungs is the Vice-Chancellor and President at the University of Technology and is a passionate advocate for innovation in the education industry. Brungs states that "Universities not only have a responsibility to prepare students for potential jobs but also to create and provide jobs for them to go too". Prior to his time at UTS Brungs worked in Australia's national science agency, CSIRO as a general manager in science investment, strategy, and performance. This role allowed Brungs to solve challenges being faced through innovative science and technology, and helped him master different disciplines for an organisation, bringing together government, research, universities, and industry. Thus, making him a key stakeholder for TechCentral. He would play a key role for our second lever due to his influence in both tertiary education and the industry.

David Thodey is the Chair of the Commonwealth Science, Industry and Research Organisation (CSIRO), Xero and Tyro Payments, and previously was known as the Chief Executive Officer and Executive Director of Telstra. With his experience as CSIRO chair and former Telstra chief helping him connect between entrepreneurs, researchers, businesses, and the community, David Thodey has actively been able to bring Tech Central to its full potential. Thus, utilising his role to better contribute technical expertise for cloud analytics, cyber security, and platform services. David Thodey would also play a critical role in shaping the local narrative surrounding innovation in the EE. He can effectively guide the direction of the industry to reach creative and social sectors as well.

Monica Barone has been the Chief Executive Officer of the City of Sydney since 2006. During this period Barone has overseen the development and implementation of the city's long-term vision of creating a sustainable and innovative environment for Central Sydney. With focus on one of Sydney's major projects being the \$13 billion Green Square Urban Renewal site, Barone has effectively revitalised the heritage and charm of the city area. The Green Square puts forth an innovative and sustainable design, providing an inviting environment for all who work, live, and visit the area. With over \$540 million being used to create community facilities, it can be assured that the innovative new library and plaza, along with the creative hub will have great purpose with the launch of TechCentral, ensuring growth, development and innovation in a sustainable manner. She will be influential in making sure the City of Sydney's plans are more collaborative in the future and stakeholders with less visibility, as well as the younger generation will have more of a platform in the EE.

All activators play a key role in reconstructing the narrative surrounding techcentral and broadening the focus beyond technological innovation, whilst collaborating with educational institutions and other stakeholders that have less visibility in the ecosystem.

3.4 (Little) Why

The leverage suggestions are evidently capable of generating considerable value for the city of Sydney based on the group's navigation of the past, present, and future entrepreneurial ecosystems. The proposal's activators will be critical in implementing the leverage. As previously stated, the leverage concept adds benefit to the local community, particularly those involved in innovation and entrepreneurship. The Sydney ecosystem is still in its infancy. As a result, many Australian companies are at the lower end of the risk spectrum. They are frequently focused on tiny niches and domestic markets, or they are built on a business strategy with immediate revenue-generating potential, such as the usual tech start-ups. There are only a few sustainable and innovative high-risk firms, which target large global markets. While 30% of Australian companies believe their target market is worth more than \$1 billion, 27% believe it is worth less than \$10 million (City of Sydney, 2016). This is a concerning statistic, since it does not justify the risks involved in establishing a business, especially when considering that scalable start-ups should aim for a billion-dollar market valuation.

These idealistic businesses mature into industry-defining businesses that employ many people. This predicament reflects a scarcity of aspirational Australian entrepreneurs who are launching sustainable businesses and pursuing large markets. Thus, our leverage proposal entails shifting focus from low-risk tech start-ups to more sustainable start-ups, as this answers the issue of lack of high-risk start-ups, and sustainable start-ups are generally value-driven and feed back into the local community and EE. With a coordinated effort by entrepreneurs, educators, the government, and corporate Australia, the Australian start-up industry has the potential to provide \$109 billion, or 4% of GDP, to the Australian economy and 540,000 employment by 2033. When compared to other start-up ecosystems, there is no better moment to be an entrepreneur in Australia, but reaching the expected economic impact would need a major and sustained effort to inspire more individuals to establish sustainable high-risk businesses. Acting on this transformation first allows for the development of policies that will allow for the expansion of social resources within the local community and the ecosystem, such as funding, international competitiveness, and job creation. In terms of physical infrastructure, Tech Central is aggressively seeking an identity as a high-tech, high-quality area that is beneficial to our environment and well-being, making it an ideal place for collaboration with sustainable start-ups. The geographical region of Tech Central is highly industrialised; therefore, in order to undergo a green transformation, the project requires significant modifications in the development concept, thus Tech Central collaborating with sustainable start-ups in the community would create a domino effect by which there is increase of start-ups in the community that utilize green practices, ultimately benefiting the environment. In this way, a city may build a lifecycle based on the triple helix by providing the atmosphere, infrastructure, and education necessary for sustainable start-ups to develop innovations that then feed back into the city.

Currently, there's also a narrow focus towards STEM students, and we suggest that educational institutions should nurture a more diverse range of students to contribute to Tech Central and the innovative community. These levers and activators will encourage ecosystem change by serving as a catalyst for the desired consequences. All stakeholders gain value from this proposed leverage as engaging with the EE would improve and diversify the flow of talent from educational institutions to companies by not just nurturing STEM students. Second, an increase in talent movement within the Tech Central can serve as a catalyst for direct job creation in the area. Furthermore, an increase in inclusion and diversity within the EE's community would allow for a better platform for indigenous voices and the Gadigal people in particular. Ultimately, diversifying the talent flow of Tech Central will encourage the production of innovative and disruptive ideas and concepts, ultimately creating an environment where high-risk sustainable start-ups are increasingly pursued.

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